
Exploring Trends in STEM Education: Insights from a Pilot Survey of Educators Using Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to expand in education, schools must determine how to implement these tools effectively and ethically. This pilot study examined perspectives of 39 secondary STEM educators regarding teacher use, student use, and ethical scenarios surrounding AI in order to inform professional development for AI implementation in schools. Survey findings indicated that many educators saw value in AI for instruction, assessment, and student support, but a substantial portion felt unprepared to use it effectively. Participation in professional development was associated with greater confidence, understanding, and classroom use of AI. Educators also drew clear ethical distinctions between using AI as a tool for support, tutoring, and idea generation and using it in ways that undermine student thinking or academic integrity. These findings suggest that successful AI integration requires targeted professional development, clear district guidance, and support for ethical, pedagogically grounded implementation.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI); stem; middle and high school; professional development

Introduction

The increasing availability of focused and effective artificial intelligence (AI) tools for educators such as Magic School, Perplexity, Khan Academy, Diffit, ChatGPT, and Class Companion, has forced districts to make decisions regarding their implementation in educators' administrative and pedagogical practices. Despite the accessibility of these tools, many educators remain hesitant to implement AI for teacher and student because of concerns related to trust in the technology's content knowledge, gaps in implementation knowledge, and misconceptions about its capabilities stemming from limited familiarity and insufficient professional development (Nazaretsky et al., 2022; Park et al., 2023). AI tools have advanced considerably in areas such as generative coding, dataset generation, and data-informed simulation and tracking (Antonenko & Abramowitz, 2022; Erduran, 2023). As a result, science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) educators must be prepared to help students understand AI's impact on the nature of science and on how scientific knowledge is interpreted.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence in STEM Education

Due to AI's rapid growth, schools often struggle to implement it effectively as an educational tool. Teacher's pedagogical capabilities related to AI may decline rather than improve when inadequate preparation and unclear policies are provided (Ghamrawi et al., 2024). Although AI has not yet revolutionized pedagogical practice, its successful implementation requires a balance between sound instructional strategies and the technology itself (Díaz & Nussbaum, 2024). When a balance is achieved, AI can provide real-time feedback and support for students while also enabling teachers to enhance lessons and make them more effective, meaningful, and engaging (AlKanaan, 2022). In STEM education, principles such as collaborative learning, adaptive learning, and critical thinking may further increase student engagement and improve learning outcomes (Dimitriadou and Lanitis, 2023).

A recent study by Akhmadieva et al. (2023) used bibliometric analysis to identify three major themes representing high-impact areas for the use of AI in STEM education: enhancing learning experiences, advancing assessment methodologies, and empowering educators. Enhanced learning experiences include not only immersive environments, such as virtual or augmented reality, but also improved accessibility. Examples include translating or dictating laboratory procedures through text-to-speech in English or other languages, adjusting laboratory equipment settings, providing support through a virtual tutor or laboratory assistant, improving safety procedures, and assisting with the organization and calculation of data (Watters et al., 2020).

Advancing assessment methodologies includes providing timely feedback, streamlining administrative and grade book tasks, and improving instructional efficiency by reducing time spent grading. These improvements can be achieved through algorithms based on natural language processing, regression analysis, visual recognition, and prediction technologies (Jia et al., 2024). Although these applications could substantially influence how STEM educators interact with students, they currently only account for 8% of AI use among STEM educators in the classroom (Jia et al., 2024).

Professional Development

Professional development is an essential component of educator growth at all career stages and levels of experience. By promoting a growth mindset, schools can ensure that teachers not only model lifelong learning but also remain current with instructional best practices, educational research, and strategies that maximize student outcomes. A recent meta-analysis by Donath et al. (2023) found a positive correlation between teacher professional development and improvements in content knowledge instructional knowledge, teaching skills, and beliefs about student performance and behavior.

Within STEM education specifically, an additional meta-analysis highlighted the significant role of professional development in strengthening teacher self-efficacy, particularly with regard to STEM pedagogy, preparation, and instructional qualifications (Zhou et al., 2023).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study was informed by established theories of educational technology adoption and technology integration, specifically the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM; Davis, 1989) and the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge framework (TPACK; Mishra & Koehler, 2006), as well as emerging literature related to AI in education. The TAM suggests that individuals' adoption of new technologies is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989), both of which are relevant in understanding educators' willingness to incorporate AI tools into instructional practice. The TPACK framework further emphasizes the interaction between technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge, providing an appropriate lens for examining AI integration in classrooms (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Collectively, these frameworks informed the development of this study related to educator familiarity with AI, instructional implementation, perceived benefits and barriers, ethical considerations, and professional development needs.

Purpose and Research Questions

In this pilot study, the perspectives of Midwest (United States) secondary STEM educators were examined through survey analysis to better understand current trends in AI comfort levels and the implementation of AI instruction, assessment, and lesson preparation. Survey data can provide valuable insight into the effectiveness of professional development and the types of support STEM educators find most meaningful as they navigate emerging AI technologies. The purpose of this study was to examine STEM educators' perspectives on teacher use, student use, and ethical scenarios surrounding artificial intelligence in order to inform professional development approaches for AI implementation in schools.

This study is significant because it addresses the gap between the increasing availability of AI tools in education and educators' preparedness to use them effectively, ethically, and confidently in STEM classrooms. As schools continue to adopt AI technologies, understanding teachers' perspectives, concerns, and professional learning needs is essential for developing effective implementation strategies. Findings from this study may help school administrators, professional development staff, and policymakers design targeted supports that strengthen teacher capacity, encourage responsible AI integration, and promote equitable student access to emerging technologies.

A survey was distributed to secondary STEM educators to address four primary research questions:

1. What are secondary STEM educators' perspectives on the current use of AI in their teaching practices, and how do these perspectives influence their approach to integrating AI in the classroom?
2. What are secondary STEM educators' perspectives on the impact of AI on student learning outcomes and engagement?
3. What are the ethical perspectives of STEM educators on the implementation and use of AI in the classroom?
4. Did participation in targeted professional development opportunities influence teachers' integration and utilization of AI tools in the classroom?

Method

Survey Design and Data Collection Procedures

To investigate the perspectives on and use of artificial intelligence in the contemporary STEM classroom, a survey was developed from established theories of educational technology adoption and technology integration, specifically TAM and TPACK frameworks. The survey was designed and distributed via Google Forms in April 2024 as part of this pilot study. Prior to distribution, the study received ethics approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) committee. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were required to provide informed consent before completing the survey.

The survey was distributed to Directors of Curriculum from one state in the Midwest (United States). Additionally, the survey was also distributed to several school districts across multiple states in the region. Each Director of Curriculum and school district offered the survey to STEM educators in their

respective districts via email invitation, although participation remained voluntary and no expectation of survey completion was communicated. Surveys were distributed to school districts by researchers where relationships were already established. For the remaining survey distributions, the Directors of Curriculum were contacted in one state through an established relationship with one Director with access to the group.

For the purposes of this study, surveys were distributed to STEM educators representing a broad range of subject areas. STEM educators were operationally defined as middle and high school teachers providing instruction in mathematics, science, technology and computer science, and engineering or applied technology courses. This definition reflects commonly used classifications of STEM education in K-12 settings and was intended to capture educators in traditional academic disciplines.

The survey consisted of three primary sections: (1) AI usage by teachers; (2) AI usage by students; and, (3) Ethical scenarios surrounding AI. Additionally, demographic information was collected including grade level taught, subjects taught, gender, race/ethnicity, age, years of experience, and highest level of education. Participant identities were not recorded, ensuring that all responses remained anonymous.

Participants

A total of 39 participants completed the pilot survey. Participant demographics are detailed in Table 1. The majority of respondents taught at the high school level ($n=25$), with science only being the most commonly taught subject ($n=23$). There were more female respondents ($n=22$) compared to males ($n=16$), and the vast majority of participants identified as White/Caucasian ($n=37$). Most respondents were between the ages of 30-39 ($n=13$) or 40-49 ($n=10$), and the most common teaching experience ranges was 6-10 years ($n=12$).

Survey Instrument

A copy of the survey instrument is provided in Attachment. Because the use of artificial intelligence in K-12 school settings is an emerging area of practice and research, no established survey instrument was identified that adequately addressed the specific constructs examined in this study. Therefore, the survey instrument was developed by the researchers based on a review of existing literature on artificial intelligence in education and consultation with local school districts to ensure relevance to current classroom contexts and educator experiences. These developmental steps were used to support the content relevance and clarity of instrument items.

The survey included seven demographic questions and two open-ended questions regarding AI tools utilized in the classroom. The instrument was divided into three main sections: AI usage by teachers, AI usage by students, and ethical scenarios related to AI. As a pilot-study instrument, the survey was designed to gather preliminary evidence regarding educator perceptions and experiences with AI and to inform future refinement and validation of the measure.

In the first section, teachers were asked a series of 14 questions about their use of AI in the classroom (AI Usage by Teachers). Examples items included, 'Artificial Intelligence is an integral part of my classroom' and, 'I understand artificial intelligence well enough to use it in my classroom.' Responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1=strongly agree, 2=agree, 3=neutral, 4=disagree, 5=strongly disagree).

Section two asked teachers to respond to nine questions about how students utilize AI in the classroom (AI Usage by Students). Example items included, 'My students use artificial intelligence without prompting from me' and, 'My students desire to implement artificial intelligence in their work.' Responses were also measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1=strongly agree, 2=agree, 3=neutral, 4=disagree, 5=strongly disagree).

Table 1.
Participant Demographics

Measures	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Grade level taught	Middle School	11	28.2
	High School	25	64.1
	Both	3	7.7
Subjects taught	Science	23	59
	Math	6	15.4
	Other	5	12.8
Gender	Multiple	5	12.8
	Male	16	41
	Female	22	56.4
Race/Ethnicity	Prefer not to say	1	2.6
	White/Caucasian	37	94.9
	Asian/Pacific Islander	1	2.6
Age	Prefer not to say	1	2.6
	20-29	7	17.9
	30-39	13	33.3
	40-49	10	25.6
	50-59	7	17.9
	60+	1	2.6
	Prefer not to say	1	2.6
Length of Teaching	<5 years	8	20.5
	6-10 years	12	30.8
	11-15 years	4	10.3
	16-20 years	4	10.3
	21-25 years	6	15.4
Education Level	>25 years	5	12.8
	Bachelors	10	25.6
	Masters	27	69.2
	Specialist	1	2.6
	Prefer not to say	1	2.6

Note. Total $n = 39$.

The third section of the survey instrument asked teachers to respond to a series of 25 questions regarding ethical scenarios surrounding the use of AI in the classroom (Ethical Scenarios Surrounding AI). Example items included, 'A teacher disregards copyright infringement by an AI model used in class' and, 'A teacher encourages the use of an AI tool without cybersecurity safeguards put in place.' Responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1=strongly ethical, 2=ethical, 3=neutral, 4=unethical, 5=strongly unethical).

Given the newly developed nature of the instrument, full psychometric validation had not been established at the time of the pilot study. As such, findings should be interpreted as exploratory. Future research should examine the instrument's psychometric properties more fully, including internal consistency reliability and additional forms of validity evidence, such as construct validity and factor structure.

Data Analyses

Data preparation and analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 28.0. Raw questionnaire data including Likert-scale responses are reported for each of the three major sections of the survey by frequency (n-size) and percentage (%) including AI Usage by Teachers (Table 2), AI Usage by Students (Table 3), and Ethical Scenarios Surrounding AI (Table 4).

To assess the impact of professional development (PD) on AI usage by teachers and students, a grouping variable was created. Teachers who indicated that their district provides training on AI by responding "strongly agree" or "agree" were classified into Group 1 (PD exposure, $n=22$). Teachers who responded "neutral," "disagree," or "strongly disagree" were classified into Group 2 (limited/no PD exposure, $n=17$).

An independent samples t-test was conducted to examine mean differences between the two groups on the AI usage by teachers and AI usage by students sections. The independent samples t-test was selected despite the ordinal nature of Likert-scale data because prior research has demonstrated that parametric tests such as the t-test are robust to violations of normality when applied to Likert-scale data, particularly when scales are treated as approximately continuous and group sizes are similar (De Winter & Dodou, 2010). Additionally, analyzing items individually rather than as aggregated composites allowed for a more granular examination of educator perspectives across specific AI-related topics, which was consistent with the exploratory aims of this pilot study. Statistical significance was evaluated at the $p < .05$ level. Results of the independent samples t-tests are presented in Table 5.

Assumptions of homogeneity of variance were examined prior to analyses using Levene's Test. Results indicated that the assumption of equal variances was met for the majority of items ($p > .05$). For the four survey questions in which Levene's test was significant, the unequal variances version of the independent samples *t*-test (Welch's *t*) was interpreted. Because the independent samples t-test is generally robust to modest departures from normality and the group sizes were similar, the use of parametric analyses was retained. In addition, the Mann-Whitney *U* test analyses were conducted for items with variance differences and produced comparable results.

The survey also included two open-ended questions designed to capture qualitative data on AI tool usage. The two questions included: (1) What AI tools are you currently using within the structure of your classroom? And, (2) What AI tools have your students used to assist in their overall education? Responses to these items were analyzed using frequency-based content analysis, in which answers were reviewed, grouped by tool or theme, and ranked by the number of respondents who mentioned each. This approach was selected to identify the most commonly referenced tools and patterns of use among respondents and to complement the quantitative Likert-scale data.

Findings

AI Usage by Teachers

Participant responses to the AI Usage by Teachers survey items are summarized in Table 2. Results indicated that in the area of educator readiness and intentions for integrating AI in the classroom, teachers agree or strongly agree that they need more training to effectively implement AI in their classroom (69.2%), they plan to integrate more AI within their classroom (61.6%), and they will use training to increase their understanding of AI (79.5%). Additionally, 66.7% of teachers agreed or strongly agreed that their district supported the use of AI in the classroom.

Conversely, in the area of understanding AI and classroom integration, a significant proportion of teachers disagreed or strongly disagreed that AI was currently an integral part of their classroom (69.2%) and that their district provided governing language on the use of AI (51.3%). Teachers were generally divided on whether or not they had a good understanding of AI and how it helps students learn.

AI Usage by Students

Participant responses to the AI Usage by Students survey items are summarized in Table 3. Results indicated that in the area of district support and policy, 61.6% of teachers agreed or strongly agreed that they understand the privacy concerns of AI, and 64.1% agreed or strongly agreed that student data privacy is a concern.

Table 2.
AI Usage by Teachers

Question/Prompts	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
AI is utilized in my classroom.	2 (5.1%)	14 (35.9%)	8 (20.5%)	10 (25.6%)	5 (12.8%)
AI is an integral part of my classroom.	0	5 (12.8%)	7 (17.9%)	17 (43.6%)	10 (25.6%)
I understand AI well enough to use it in my classroom.	4 (10.3%)	18 (46.2%)	6 (15.4%)	9 (23.1%)	2 (5.1%)
I need more training to effectively use AI in my classroom.	7(17.9%)	20 (51.3%)	8 (20.5%)	4 (10.3%)	0
I plan to integrate more AI within my classroom.	4 (10.3%)	20 (51.3%)	10 (25.6%)	4 (10.3%)	1 (2.6%)
I will use training to increase my understanding of AI.	6 (15.4%)	25 (64.1%)	5 (12.8%)	3 (7.7%)	0
I desire to incorporate AI within my classroom but am ill-equipped to do so.	3 (7.7%)	5 (12.8%)	17 (43.6%)	11 (28.2%)	3 (7.7%)
I hope to primarily use AI for my benefit – assistance in grading, lesson planning, etc.	5 (12.8%)	17 (43.6%)	14 (35.9%)	0	3 (7.7%)
I hope to primarily use AI as a tool to assist student learning.	1 (2.6%)	16 (41.0%)	12 (30.8%)	9 (23.1%)	1 (2.6%)
I am comfortable instructing my students on how to use AI to their benefit.	1 (2.6%)	7 (17.9%)	11 (28.2%)	15 (38.5%)	5 (12.8%)
I have a good understanding of AI and how it helps my students learn.	2 (5.1%)	8 (20.5%)	15 (38.5%)	12 (30.8%)	2 (5.1%)
My district supports the use of AI in the classroom.	9 (23.1%)	17 (43.6%)	10 (25.6%)	3 (7.7%)	0
My district provides governing language on the use of AI.	2 (5.1%)	8 (20.5%)	9 (23.1%)	16 (41.0%)	4 (10.3%)
My district provides training on the use of AI.	1 (2.6%)	21 (53.8%)	11 (28.2%)	4 (10.3%)	2 (5.1%)

Note. Total $n = 39$.

Ethical Scenarios Surrounding AI

Responses to the Ethical Scenarios Surrounding AI are summarized in Table 4. In the area of ethical and practical considerations of using AI in educational settings, 82% of respondents found that teachers disregarding copyright infringement by an AI model used in class was unethical or strongly unethical, and 94.9% of respondents indicated that a teacher encouraging the use of an AI tool without knowledge of its extended data storage features was unethical or strongly unethical. Nearly 75% of respondents indicated that teachers making a student use an AI tool even though the student has raised valid concerns about the privacy of the required tool was unethical or strongly unethical.

In the area of student and teacher utilization of AI tools for academic projects and learning, 89.8% of respondents said that a student developing an idea for a project using a generative AI bot but not using any writing by both was strongly ethical or ethical, 77% of respondents indicated that a teacher developing a project-based learning lesson with the use of AI was strongly ethical or ethical, and 89.8% of respondents indicated that students developing problem sets using an AI tool to garner a greater understanding of content was strongly ethical or ethical. Additionally, 87.2% of respondents indicated that students using a step-by-step AI solver to check their work on a problem set was strongly ethical or ethical, and 71.8% of respondents indicated that a teacher encouraging students to use AI as a method for researching scientific topics was strongly ethical or ethical.

Table 3.
AI Usage by Students

Question/Prompts	Strong Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Student data privacy is a concern for me with AI.	4 (10.3%)	21 (53.8%)	7 (17.9%)	7 (17.9%)	0
I understand the privacy concerns surrounding AI.	4 (10.3%)	20 (51.3%)	8 (20.5%)	7 (17.9%)	0
My students use AI without prompting from me.	3 (7.7%)	17 (43.6%)	10 (25.6%)	9 (23.1%)	0
My students desire to implement AI in their work.	3 (7.7%)	19(48.7%)	12 (30.8%)	4 (10.3%)	1 (2.6%)
AI increases student creativity.	1 (2.6%)	7 (17.9%)	13 (33.3%)	15 (38.5%)	3 (7.7%)
AI increases teacher creativity.	4 (10.3%)	15 (38.5%)	15 (38.5%)	4 (10.3%)	1 (2.6%)
*The use of AI limits student thought.	3 (7.7%)	15 (38.5%)	12 (30.8%)	8 (20.5%)	0
AI prevents students from creating unique projects.	3 (7.7%)	12 (30.8%)	9 (23.1%)	14 (35.9%)	1 (2.6%)
My students are comfortable with AI tools.	1 (2.6%)	10 (25.6%)	(35.9%)	12 (30.8%)	2 (5.1%)

Note. Total N = 39 with the exception of one question.

*Total N = 38.

Professional Development (PD)

Significant differences between teachers with PD exposure and teachers with limited/no PD exposure were found on several survey items and are summarized in Table 5. Significant differences were found for teachers who PD exposure on items including: AI is utilized in my classroom ($t_{(37)} = -3.94, p < .001$), AI is an integral part of my classroom ($t_{(37)} = -2.51, p < .001$), I understand AI well enough to use it in my classroom ($t_{(37)} = -2.37, p = .012$), and my district supports the use of AI in the classroom ($t_{(37)} = -2.75, p = .005$). Additionally, significant differences were found for teachers with PD exposure on additional items including: I will use training to increase my understanding of AI ($t_{(37)} = -2.12, p = .020$), I am comfortable instructing my students on how to use AI to their benefit ($t_{(37)} = -1.98, p = .027$), and AI increases teacher creativity ($t_{(37)} = -1.99, p = .027$).

Table 4.
Ethical Scenarios Surrounding AI

Question/Prompts	Strong Ethical	Ethical	Neutral	Unethical	Strongly Unethical
A teacher disregards copyright infringement by an AI model used in class.	0	1 (2.6%)	6 (15.4%)	24 (61.5%)	8 (20.5%)
A teacher encourages the use of an AI tool without cybersecurity safeguards put in place.	0	0	2 (5.1%)	28 (71.8%)	9 (23.1%)
A teacher uses an AI tool without knowledge of its extended data storage feature.	0	2 (5.1%)	16 (41.0%)	18 (46.2%)	3 (7.7%)
A teacher knowingly uses an AI bot that stores inputted data from the AI's metadata.	0	5(12.8%)	19 (48.7%)	12 (30.8%)	3 (7.7%)
A student develops an idea for a project using a generative AI bot but does not use any writing done by the bot.	4 (10.3%)	31 (79.5%)	2 (5.1%)	2 (5.1%)	0
A student develops an idea for a project using a generative AI bot and uses some writing done by the bot.	0	9 (23.1%)	10 (25.6%)	20 (51.3%)	0

Table 4 (continued)

A student uses an AI bot to “heighten” their vocabular for a project or paper.	2 (5.1%)	21 (53.8%)	8 (20.5%)	8 (20.5%)	0
A student develops presentation and paper graphics by using an Art AI, as opposed to creating it themselves.	2 (5.1%)	12 (30.8%)	13 (33.3%)	11	1 (2.6%)
A teacher develops a project-based learning lesson with the use of AI.	4 (10.3%)	26 (66.7%)	8 (20.5%)	1 (2.6%)	0
Students develop problem sets using an AI tool to garner a greater understanding of content.	4 (10.3%)	31 (79.5%)	4 (10.3%)	0	0
Students use generative AI to edit written papers and projects.	0	7 (17.9%)	13 (33.3%)	16 (41.0%)	3 (7.7%)
Students develop a step-by-step AI solver to work through problem sets.	2 (5.1%)	13 (33.3%)	17 (42.6%)	7 (17.9%)	0
Students who have already mastered content use a step-by-step AI solver to complete homework.	1 (2.6%)	6 (15.4%)	10 (25.6%)	20 (51.3%)	2 (5.1%)
Students use a step-by-step AI solver to check their work on a problem set.	2 (5.1%)	32 (82.1%)	4 (10.3%)	1 (2.6%)	0
A teacher encourages students to write a paper with the assistance of AI.	2 (5.1%)	16 (41.0%)	12 (30.8%)	8 (20.5%)	0
A teacher encourages students to use AI as a method for researching scientific topics.	4 (10.3%)	24 (61.5%)	8 (20.5%)	3 (7.7%)	0
A teacher uses AI to grade student work entirely.	1 (2.6%)	3 (7.7%)	11 (28.2%)	20 (51.3%)	4 (10.3%)
A teacher uses AI to assist in grading student assignments.	1 (2.6%)	29 (74.4%)	6 (15.4%)	3 (7.7%)	0
A district requires all classes to utilize AI within their classroom in some respect.	2 (5.1%)	3 (7.7%)	18 (46.2%)	14 (35.9%)	2 (5.1%)
A teacher uses a generative AI tool for rubric development and lesson planning but does not inform students of usage.	1 (2.6%)	18 (46.2%)	13 (33.3%)	7 (17.9%)	0
A district prevents teachers from using AI in their classrooms.	0	0	15 (38.5%)	20 (51.3%)	4 (10.3%)
A teacher avoids using AI because they feel the like technology will be detrimental to students future.	0	7 (17.9%)	15 (38.5%)	14 (35.9%)	3 (7.7%)
A teacher makes a student use an AI tool even though they show apprehension towards the technology.	0	5 (12.8%)	16 (41.%)	18 (46.2%)	0
A teacher makes a student use an AI tool even though they student has raised valid concerns about the privacy of the required tool.	0	1 (2.6%)	9 (23.1%)	25 (64.1%)	4 (10.3%)
A teacher intentionally develops an incorrect solution by AI to encourage students to avoid the technology at all costs.	0	3 (7.7%)	10 (25.6%)	22 (56.4%)	4 (10.3%)

Note. Total $n = 39$

Significant differences were also found for teachers with limited/no PD exposure on the item I need more training to effectively use AI in my classroom ($t_{(37)} = 1.88, p=.034$). Effect sizes (Cohen’s d) were calculated for all significant findings and interpreted using conventional benchmarks (Cohen, 1988). Effect sizes ranged from medium to large across all significant items: AI is utilized in my classroom ($d=1.30$, large), AI is an integral part of my classroom ($d=0.83$, large), my district supports the use of AI in the classroom ($d=0.90$, large), I understand AI well enough to use it in my classroom ($d=0.78$, medium), I will use training to increase my understanding of AI ($d=0.70$, medium), AI increases teacher creativity ($d=0.65$, medium), I am comfortable instructing my students on how to use

AI to their benefit ($d=0.65$, medium), and I need more training to effectively use AI in my classroom ($d=0.62$, medium). These effect sizes suggest the differences between teachers with and without professional development exposure are not only statistically significant, but practically meaningful. These findings highlight the potential impact of professional development on teachers' perceptions of AI use in educational settings.

Table 5.

Differences Between Teachers Who Received and Did Not Receive Professional Development and AI Usage in the Classroom

	PD Exposure ($n=22$)		Limited/ no PD ($n=17$)		<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>				
AI is utilized in my classroom.	2.50	1.01	3.76	.97	37	-3.94	<.001*	1.30
AI is an integral part of my classroom.	3.50	1.06	4.24	.66	37	-2.51	<.001*	0.83
I understand AI well enough to use it in my classroom.	2.32	1.00	3.12	1.11	37	-2.37	.012*	0.78
I need more training to effectively use AI in my classroom.	2.45	.91	1.94	.75	37	1.88	.034*	0.62
I plan to integrate more AI within my classroom.	2.27	.94	2.65	.86	37	-1.28	.208	0.42
I will use training to increase my understanding of AI.	1.91	.68	2.41	.80	37	-2.12	.020*	0.70
I desire to incorporate AI within my classroom but am ill-equipped to do so.	3.14	1.21	3.18	.73	37	-1.21	.452	0.40
I hope to primarily use AI for my benefit – assistance in grading, lesson planning, etc.	2.41	1.05	2.53	.94	37	-.37	.357	0.12
I hope to primarily use AI as a tool to assist student learning.	2.91	1.02	2.71	.77	37	.684	.249	0.22
I am comfortable instructing my students on how to use AI to their benefit.	3.14	1.04	3.76	.90	37	-1.98	.027*	0.65
I have a good understanding of AI and how it helps my students learn.	2.91	1.02	3.35	.86	37	-1.44	.079	0.47
My district supports the use of AI in the classroom.	1.86	.83	2.59	.80	37	-2.75	.005*	0.90
My district provides governing language on the use of AI.	3.14	1.28	3.53	.72	37	-1.13	.133	0.37
Student data privacy is a concern for me with AI.	2.50	1.06	2.35	.70	37	.494	.312	0.16
I understand the privacy concerns surrounding AI.	2.45	1.06	2.47	.72	37	-.054	.479	0.02
My students use AI without prompting from me.	2.45	.96	2.88	.86	37	-1.44	.079	0.47
My students desire to implement AI in their work.	2.36	1.00	2.71	.69	37	-1.21	.118	0.40
AI increases student creativity.	3.27	1.08	3.35	.79	37	-.258	.399	0.08
AI increases teacher creativity.	2.32	1.00	2.88	.70	37	-1.99	.027*	0.65
^a The use of AI limits student thought.	2.67	.97	2.65	.86	36	.065	.474	0.02
AI prevents students from creating unique projects.	3.05	1.09	2.82	1.02	37	.649	.260	0.21
My students are comfortable with AI tools.	2.95	1.00	3.29	.85	37	-1.12	.134	0.37

Note. Total $n = 39$ with the exception of one question.

^aTotal $n = 38$, * $p < .05$

Qualitative Responses

Responses to the two open-ended questions regarding AI tool usage revealed notable patterns in both teacher and student practice. When asked what AI tools they currently use within the structure of their classroom, the most frequently cited responses included: non, ChatGPT, Magic School AI, Diffit, and AI-assisted graphing tools. These responses suggest that while some educators have started integrating purposeful educational AI platforms, a meaningful portion of respondents reported no current use of AI tools in their instruction.

When asked what AI tools their students have used to assist in their overall education, the most common responses included: it is not allowed or I'm not sure, ChatGPT, OpenAI, AI-assisted graphing tools, and School AI. The prevalence of not allowed or I'm not sure responses among the student-use item is consistent with the quantitative findings indicating that many districts lack governing language on AI use and that a significant number of teachers are uncertain about how students are engaging with these tools outside of their direct instruction.

Discussion and Conclusions

The purpose of this pilot study was to obtain the perspectives of STEM educators on teacher use, student use, and ethical scenarios surrounding Artificial Intelligence to develop informed professional development approaches for the implementation of AI in schools. Overall, the findings suggest that secondary STEM educators recognize the growing relevance of AI in education and are interested in integrating these tools into their practice, yet many do not feel adequately prepared to do so (Tables 2-4). The results also indicate that participation in professional development is associated with greater confidence, understanding, and instructional use of AI (Table 5), highlighting professional development as a key factor in successful implementation. These findings are consistent with recent literature suggesting that successful AI integration depends not only on access to tools, but also the availability of meaningful professional learning opportunities that build teacher knowledge, confidence, and instructional capacity. Recent research has similarly identified a mismatch between the rapid growth of AI in education and the professional development supports available to teachers (Tan et al., 2025).

This study highlights several important issues in education. First, the findings suggest that school districts should not assume that access to AI tools alone will lead to meaningful or effective classroom integration. Educators require structured support, clear expectations, and opportunities to build both technical knowledge and pedagogical confidence. As illustrated in Table 2, 69.2% of teachers agreed or strongly agreed they need more training to effectively use AI, yet only 56.4% agreed their district provides training. As a result, districts should prioritize sustained, targeted professional development that helps teachers understand how AI can support instruction, assessment, creativity, and student engagement within their specific content areas. This implication is reinforced by UNESCO's recent AI competency framework for teachers, which emphasizes that effective AI integration required development across multiple domains, including ethics, pedagogy, AI foundations, and professional learning (UNESCO, 2024).

Second, the findings indicate that AI implementation in education must be accompanied by clear district guidance and policy. Although many educators expressed interest in using AI, the absence of governing language, ethical guidance, and implementation frameworks may contribute to uncertainty and inconsistent use. As illustrated in Table 2, 51.3% of respondents disagreed or strong disagreed that their district provides governing language on AI use. Educational leaders should develop policies that address responsible use, academic integrity, data privacy, copyright protections, and cybersecurity while also providing practical examples of appropriate classroom applications. Clear guidance can help teachers navigate ethical boundaries and make more informed decisions about how AI should and should not be used in school settings, as further evidenced in the ethical findings summarized in Table 4. This recommendation aligns with UNESCO's guidance for generative AI in education and research, which calls on education systems to take immediate action to develop human-centered policy, build capacity, and establish safeguards for responsible implementation (Miao & Holmes, 2023).

Third, the findings have implications for student learning. Educators in this study appeared more likely to view AI as a support for idea generation, tutoring, and research than as a substitute for student thought or original work (Table 4). This suggests that schools should frame AI as a tool to enhance learning rather than replace foundational skill development. In practice, this means teachers may need support in designing learning experiences that help students use AI critically, responsibly, and transparently while still developing core knowledge and problem-solving skills. AI literacy instruction should therefore become an increasingly important part of STEM education. This interpretation is supported by OECD findings illustrating that teachers most often use AI for planning, summarizing content, and generating instructional materials, while more complex ties to assessment and student performance remain less common (OECD, 2025). Recent OECD analysis also suggests that AI should be understood less as an automatic improvement and more as a tool whose educational value depends on the pedagogical context in which it's used (OECD, 2026).

Finally, the results suggest that effective AI integration depends on meeting educators where they are in their development. As illustrated in Table 5, teachers varied in their confidence, understanding, and perceptions of ethical use, indicating a one-size-fits-all approach to implementation is unlikely to be effective. Differentiated professional development, ongoing collaboration, and opportunities for guided practice may better support educators as they learn to evaluate and integrate AI tools in ways that align with sound pedagogy and equitable access for students. This conclusion is also supported by international survey data showing that teachers report substantial professional development needs related to AI, and AI represents one of the most prominent areas of requested training (OECD, 2026).

The findings of this study, taken together with the qualitative data on tool usage, suggest that schools need a structured, multi-component framework to guide meaningful AI integration. Effective frameworks for technology integration in schools have historically emphasized the importance of coordinated actions across multiple stakeholders and domains (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), with recent research arguing that AI-specific implementation requires attention to ethics, governance, infrastructure, and professional capacity simultaneously (Miao & Holmes, 2023; UNESCO, 2024). The Fork Approach to AI integration offers one such model, developed by the authors of this study through the researchers' professional work with school districts navigating AI implementation. The term "Fork" reflects the idea that schools stand at a critical decision point in AI adoption, and that the path forward requires deliberate, parallel action across four interconnected pillars rather than a single sequential implementation strategy. The Fork Approach organizes the essential elements of responsible AI implementation across four interconnected pillars: Safeguards, Committee, Policy, and Development. The Safeguards pillar addresses the data privacy concerns and tool vetting processes that many educators in this study identified as barriers to AI adoption, ensuring that schools establish clear acceptable use parameters before tools are introduced in the classroom. The Committee pillar reflects that need for a technology-driven team of administrators, teachers, and students who are collectively dedicated to AI integration, which is consistent with this study's findings that professional development and district support are strongly associated with greater educator confidence and classroom use (Table 5). The Policy pillar directly responds to the finding that 51.3% of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed that their district providing governing language on AI, underscoring the need for formal commitments to AI literacy, tool vetting, and academic integrity. Finally, the Development pillar aligns with the study's central recommendation that teacher-led, collaborative professional learning is essential for building the instructional capacity needed to use AI effectively, ethically, and equitably in STEM classrooms. Together, these four pillars provide a practical roadmap for schools seeking to move from reactive, inconsistent AI use toward intentional, sustainable integration in the classroom.

Taken together, this study contributes preliminary evidence that AI implementation in secondary STEM education is not simply a question of technological adoption, but one of teacher preparation, ethical decision-making, and instructional design. As AI continues to evolve, educators and school systems will need to move beyond curiosity and toward intentional, supported, and pedagogically grounded use. Future research with larger and more diverse samples is needed to further examine these trends and to identify the professional development models, policies, and classroom practices that most effectively support responsible AI integration in education.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considering when interpreting the findings of this study. First, although data were collected from school districts across multiple states, the sample is not representative of the overall teacher population of the United States. The sample in this study was 94.9% non-Hispanic White, which exceeds the national proportion of teachers identified as white and limits the demographic representativeness of the findings. As a result, the perspectives reported in this study may not reflect experiences or perceptions of more diverse educator populations.

Second, the study was limited by a relatively small sample size based on survey responses, which restricted the researchers' ability to make broader comparisons across educator groups. A larger and more geographically diverse sample across the Midwest (United States) or additional regions may yield different results and provide greater insight into educators' perceptions and use of AI.

Third, the survey instrument was developed by the researchers for this pilot study because no established instrument was identified that adequately measures secondary STEM educators' perspectives on AI use, student use, and ethical scenarios in school settings. Although the instrument was informed by the existing literature and consultation with local school districts to support content relevance, full psychometric evidence, including reliability and additional forms of validity, had not yet been established at the time of data collection. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted as exploratory and preliminary.

Fourth, the study relied on self-reported survey data, which may be influenced by participant interpretation of items, social desirability, and differences in familiarity of AI terminology and tools. Because AI in education is a rapidly evolving topic, participants may also have had varying understandings of what constituted artificial intelligence, which could have influenced their responses. Future research with larger, more diverse samples and further validation of the survey instrument is needed to strengthen the generalizability of the findings.

Finally, statistical analyses were conducted at the individual item level rather than using composite sub-scale scores, which is consistent with the exploratory intent of this pilot study but increases the risk of Type I error due to the number of simultaneous comparisons performed. Given the preliminary and descriptive nature of this study, findings are intended to identify patterns and generate hypotheses for future research rather than to make confirmatory statistical claims. Future studies with larger samples should employ composite scoring or correction procedures for multiple comparisons, such as the Bonferroni or Benjamini-Hochberg method, to strengthen the rigor of inferential conclusions.

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Ethics statement: In this study, we affirm compliance with the rules outlined in the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive" and 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments", and assert that none of the "Actions Against Scientific Research and Publication Ethics" have been undertaken. Furthermore, we declare that there is no conflict of interest among the authors, that all authors have contributed to the study, and that full responsibility for any ethical violations rests with the article authors.

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AI Use Declaration: AI was not used in the development of this manuscript.

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Attachment

Survey: Artificial Intelligence in the Contemporary STEM Classroom

Questions/Prompts	Response Choices
<i>Demographics Questions</i>	
What grade level do you teach?	Middle School, High School, Both
What subjects do you teach?	Science, Math, Engineering, Technology, Other
Gender	Male, Female, Non-Binary, Other
What race or ethnicity best describes you?	American Indian or Alaskan Native, Asian/Pacific Islander, Black or African-American, Hispanic, White/Caucasian, Prefer not to say
Age	20-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59, 60+, Prefer not to say
How long have you been teaching?	<5 years, 6-10 years, 11-15 years, 16-20 years, 21-25 years, >25 years, Prefer not to say
What is your highest level of education?	Bachelor, Masters, Specialist, Doctorate, Prefer not to say
<i>Section I: AI Usage by Teachers (14 Items)</i>	
AI is utilized in my classroom.	Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral, Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)
AI is an integral part of my classroom.	SA A Neutral D SD
I understand AI well enough to use it in my classroom.	SA A Neutral D SD
I need more training to effectively use AI in my classroom.	SA A Neutral D SD
I plan to integrate more AI within my classroom.	SA A Neutral D SD
I will use training to increase my understanding of AI.	SA A Neutral D SD
I desire to incorporate AI within my classroom but am ill-equipped to do so.	SA A Neutral D SD
I hope to primarily use AI for my benefit – assistance in grading, lesson planning, etc.	SA A Neutral D SD
I hope to primarily use AI as a tool to assist student learning.	SA A Neutral D SD
I am comfortable instructing my students on how to use AI to their benefit.	SA A Neutral D SD
I have a good understanding of AI and how it helps my students learn.	SA A Neutral D SD
My district supports the use of AI in the classroom.	SA A Neutral D SD
My district provides governing language on the use of AI.	SA A Neutral D SD
My district provides training on the use of AI.	SA A Neutral D SD
<i>Section II: AI Usage by Students (9 Items)</i>	
Student data privacy is a concern for me with AI.	Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral, Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)
I understand the privacy concerns surrounding AI.	SA A Neutral D SD
My students use AI without prompting from me.	SA A Neutral D SD
My students desire to implement AI in their work.	SA A Neutral D SD
AI increases student creativity.	SA A Neutral D SD
AI increases teacher creativity.	SA A Neutral D SD
The use of AI limits student thought.	SA A Neutral D SD
AI prevents students from creating unique projects.	SA A Neutral D SD
My students are comfortable with AI tools.	SA A Neutral D SD

Section III: Ethical Scenarios Surrounding AI (25 Items)

A teacher disregards copyright infringement by an AI model used in class.	Strongly Ethical (SE), Ethical (E), Neutral, Unethical (U), Strongly Unethical (SU)
A teacher encourages the use of an AI tool without cybersecurity safeguards put in place.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher uses an AI tool without knowledge of its extended data storage feature.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher knowingly uses an AI bot that stores inputted data from the AI's metadata.	SE E Neutral U SU
A student develops an idea for a project using a generative AI bot but does not use any writing done by the bot.	SE E Neutral U SU
A student develops an idea for a project using a generative AI bot and uses some writing done by the bot.	SE E Neutral U SU
A student uses an AI bot to "heighten" their vocabular for a project or paper.	SE E Neutral U SU
A student develops presentation and paper graphics by using an Art AI, as opposed to creating it themselves.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher develops a project-based learning lesson with the use of AI.	SE E Neutral U SU
Students develop problem sets using an AI tool to garner a greater understanding of content.	SE E Neutral U SU
Students use generative AI to edit written papers and projects.	SE E Neutral U SU
Students develop a step-by-step AI solver to work through problem sets.	SE E Neutral U SU
Students who have already mastered content use a step-by-step AI solver to complete homework.	SE E Neutral U SU
Students use a step-by-step AI solver to check their work on a problem set.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher encourages students to write a paper with the assistance of AI.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher encourages students to use AI as a method for researching scientific topics.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher uses AI to grade student work entirely.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher uses AI to assist in grading student assignments.	SE E Neutral U SU
A district requires all classes to utilize AI within their classroom in some respect.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teachers uses a generative AI tool for rubric development and lesson planning but does not inform students of usage.	SE E Neutral U SU
A district prevents teachers from using AI in their classrooms.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher avoids using AI because they feel the like technology will be detrimental to students future.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher makes a student use an AI tool even though they show apprehension towards the technology.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher makes a student use an AI tool even though they student has raised valid concerns about the privacy of the required tool.	SE E Neutral U SU
A teacher intentionally develops an incorrect solution by AI to encourage students to avoid the technology at all costs.	SE E Neutral U SU
<u>Free Response</u>	
What AI tools are you currently using within the structure of your classroom?	Free
What AI tools have your students used to assist in their overall education?	Free